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FORMULATION OF CO-CRYSTAL FOR SOLUBILITY ENHANCEMENT OF CURCUMIN

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ABSTRACT

Co-crystallization holds a great potential for solving the problem of low aqueous solubility and bioavailability of drug molecules and improve the other physical properties of active pharmaceutical ingredients. The objective of this investigation was to study the effect of co-crystallization on different physicochemical properties of curcumin. In this study curcumin formed co-crystals with hydroquinone and para-benzoic acid by using spray drying technique. Preliminary evaluation for screening of co-crystals has been done by melting point and IR spectroscopy. From the results of screening it was concluded that curcumin form co-crystal with hydroquinone and para-benzoic acid i.e. CUR: HQ and CUR: PBA co-crystals. CUR: HQ and CUR: PBA co-crystals were characterised in terms of melting point, FTIR spectroscopy, differential scanning calorimetry, solubility, drug content, X-ray diffraction study, flow properties and compared with plain curcumin. CUR: HQ and CUR: PBA co-crystals had shown increase in solubility in water over plain curcumin.

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INTRODUCTION

In the Indian Ayurvedic system of herbal medicine, turmeric is known to be strengthening and warming to the whole body. Its main active constituent is curcumin (C), but despite much evidence of its efficacy and safety, it has not yet been approved as a therapeutic agent due to its low bioavailability, instability at physiological pH, insolubility in water, slow uptake by cells and rapid metabolism inside the cell. Curcumin, a hydrophobic polyphenol derived from the rhizome of the herb *Curcuma longa* has a wide spectrum of biological and pharmacological activities. Chemically, curcumin is a bis-R,-unsaturated-diketone (commonly called diferuloylmethane), which exhibits keto-enol tautomerism having a predominant keto form in acidic and neutral solutions and stable enol form in alkaline medium. [1, 2].

Solubility is the property of a solid, liquid, or gaseous chemical substance called solute to dissolve in a solid, liquid, or gaseous solvent to form a homogeneous solution of the solute in the solvent. The solubility of a substance fundamentally depends on the solvent used as well as on temperature and pressure. The extent of solubility of a substance in a specific solvent is measured as the saturation concentration where adding more solute does not increase its concentration in the solution. [3, 4] Crystal Engineering is flourishing field of research practiced by scientists which addresses crystal structural design and its fabrication to the desired quality and safety product. Crystal engineering has been described as the 'exploitation of non-covalent interactions between molecular or ionic components for the rational design of solid-state structures that might exhibit interesting electrical, magnetic and optical properties'. [5,6,7].

Co-crystals are also known by their name as "Addition Compounds" (early 1900's), "Organic Molecular Compounds" (1937), "Complexes" (1960's) or "Heteromolecular Crystals" (2005) from time to time. Co-crystals can be defined as crystalline complexes of two or more neutral molecular constituents bound together in the crystal lattice through non covalent interactions (primarily hydrogen bonding). From definition it is clear that two or more compound are held together by supramolecular synthons. Supramolecular synthons can be defined as "structural units within supermolecules which can be formed and assembled by known or conceivable intermolecular interactions". Co-crystals can be constructed through several types of interaction, including hydrogen bonding, stacking and Vander Waals forces. [8,9,10,11].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Curcumin were procured from Konark Herbals & Healthcare Mumbai, Para hydroxybenzoic acid, Hydroquinone, methanol purchased from Modern laboratory, Nashik.

Preparation of curcumin cocrystal:

The co-crystals were formed by spray drying technique. For spray drying the solution was prepared by adding CUR and HYD (1:1) molar ratio in 100ml of methanol. In which 0.88g of hydroquinone and 2.94g of curcumin was added. This solution was spray dried at 100°C inlet temperature, 40 to 60 m³/hr aspirator flow rate, 2 to 4 ml/min feed rate and 60°C outlet temperature.

Characterization of co-crystal: Melting point:

Melting point of the sample CUR-HQ 1:1 and CUR-PB 1:1 were determined by open capillary method by using melting point apparatus. The melting point was done in triplicate. [16,31,35,36]

IR Spectroscopy:

Infrared spectroscopy analysis of CUR-HQ 1:1 and CUR-PB 1:1 was performed by Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR Bruker Alpha).

Differential scanning calorimetry:

The DSC thermogram of CUR-HQ 1:1 and CUR-PB 1:1 was recorded by differential scanning calorimeter equipped with a computerized data station.

X-ray Diffraction:

For characterization of crystalline state, the powder x-ray diffraction (XRD) pattern of CUR-HQ 1:1 and CUR- PB 1:1 was determined. Powder X-ray diffraction (XRD) was carried out using a Bruker AXS Advance D-8 scanner with filter Ni, Cu- K α radiation, voltage 40kV and a current 20mA. The scanning rate employed was 1⁰/min over the 5⁰ to 50⁰ diffraction angle (2 Θ) range. [12,31]

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy:

Co-crystals were characterized by ¹H NMR to confirm their stoichiometry. Proton NMR spectra were recorded on Bruker Avance 400 MHz spectrometer (Bruker-Biospin, Karlsruhe, Germany). Chemical shifts are quoted in τ scale and J coupling in Hz. [12,32]

Solubility:

A solvent under consideration (Methanol, Ethanol, water) was saturated with co-crystals and then allow to stand at room temperature (25°C) for 3 days with frequent shaking. The supernatant solution was filtered and analyzed for drug content by using UV spectroscopy. [31,35,36,37]

Drug content:

Drug content analysis was performed in order to study the amount of drug incorporated in the co-crystals. Curcumin from co-crystals were extracted by dissolving them in Methanol. Curcumin extract was analyzed spectroscopically at respective wavelength, against Methanol as blank.

$$\% \text{ Drug content} = \frac{W_a}{W_t} \times 100$$

Where,

W_a = Actual drug content, and

W_t = Theoretical drug content

In vitro drug release:

Drug release studies of co-crystals were performed using USP dissolution apparatus II (Lab India-DS 8000) using 900ml of phosphate buffer (pH 6.8) and 0.1N HCl as a medium at $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$. The speed of the paddle was adjusted to 75rpm. Curcumin co-crystals (equivalent to 10mg of curcumin) was added in dissolution media. At predetermined time intervals an aliquot (5ml) of the sample was collected, filtered and analyzed for the content of curcumin by UV spectroscopy. An equivalent volume (5ml) of fresh dissolution medium was added to compensate for the loss due to sampling to maintain sink condition. [24,25,26].

RESULTS & DISCUSSIONS

After screening of cofomers listed in Table 1, infrared spectra of hydroquinone and para-hydroxy benzoic acid shows shift in peak of -OH group and lowering of melting point indicates presence of non-covalent interaction between curcumin and hydroquinone, para-hydroxy benzoic acid.

Table 1: List of cocrystal former used in study.

Sr.No.	Cocrystal Former
1	Succinic Acid
2	Hydroquinone
3	Fumaric Acid
4	Lauric Acid
5	P-Hydroxybenzoic Acid

Mutual solubility is important parameter in selection of a solvent. Mutual solubility means, solubility parameter of the drug and that of the co-crystal former in common solvent do not differ too much. After contemplating that all criteria DMSO, Ethanol, Methanol were studied and from that Methanol was selected as solvent.

Melting point:

The melting point of a compound is a fundamental physical property determined for the purpose of characterization or purity identification of a compound. It was observed that the co-crystals of Curcumin prepared with Hydroquinone have shown melting point in the range of $137-139^\circ\text{C}$ i.e. melting point below the melting points of pure drug Curcumin ($180-183^\circ\text{C}$) and hydroquinone ($169-171^\circ\text{C}$). The melting point of CUR-PB co-crystals was determined in triplicate and was found to be $157-159^\circ\text{C}$ and melting point of p-hydroxybenzoic acid ($215-217^\circ\text{C}$).

IR spectroscopy:

Figure1: IR spectroscopy of Curcumin, C+HQ, C+PB.

The possible interaction between CUR: HQ and CUR: PB was studied by IR Spectroscopy. Curcumin showed the structural characteristic peaks because of C=O (ketone), OH, C=C (alkene), -C=C- aromatic ring, ester -C-O- stretching as shown in table.

From the IR spectra, it was observed that all important peaks because of functional group of drug are present in co-crystals along with some shift in peaks indicating the presence of hydrogen bonding that had occurred in co-crystals.

DSC: CUR:

CUR+HYD:

CUR+PB:

Figure No: 2 Shows DSC thermogram of a) CUR b) CUR- HQ c) CUR- PB.

The thermogram of Curcumin had shown single endothermic peak maxima at 179.53°C due to melting of drug shown in fig. The thermal behavior was distinct, with a different melting transition from that seen with either of the individual component; this suggest formation of new phase: CUR-HQ, CUR-PB co-crystals. The melting point of CUR-HQ and CUR-PB was found to be below the melting point of both the drug and co-crystal former. A single endothermic transition for the CUR-HQ and CUR-PB co-crystals indicates the absence of any unbound or absorbed solvent or water and also demonstrates the stability of the phase until the melting point.

X-ray Diffraction:

a) Curcumin

c) CUR-PB

Figure No: 3 Shows X-ray diffraction pattern of CUR, CUR-HQ, CUR-PB.

Powder X-ray diffraction studies of curcumin shown in Figure 3. The pure curcumin exhibited intense crystalline peak between 5° to 50° . Characteristic diffraction peaks at 17.6° , 23.6° , 24.7° , 27° and 30° were observed with intense peak at 24.7° indicating crystalline nature of curcumin. While CUR-HQ and CUR-PBA shows characteristic peak at 18.5° , 21.55° , 23.05° , 29° and 17.4° , 23.4° , 25.65° , 27.4° respectively. The shift in intense peak indicate formation of new crystalline form.

Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectroscopy:

a) Curcumin

Drug content:

The content of Curcumin from CUR-HQ, CUR-PB, co-crystals had been found as shown in Table 3. The drug content in every case was found to be within standard assay limit of Curcumin.

Table 3: The drug content of Curcumin from CUR-HQ, CUR-PB co-crystals.

Sr.No.	Cocrystal Sample	Cocrystal (mg)	Theoretical Drug Content(mg)	Drug recovery (mg) (n=3)	% Drug recovery
1	CUR-HQ	10	7.70	7.60	98.70 ± 0.13
2	CUR-PBA	10	7.28	7.09	97.39 ± 0.31

In-vitro Dissolution Study:

In vitro drug release studies were performed for pure curcumin and its cocrystal in the phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and 0.1N HCl. Results revealed that the dissolution of pure curcumin was just 13% release in 120 min. The pure curcumin exhibited the slowest dissolution rate because of its hydrophobicity that caused the powder to float on the surface of the dissolution medium and prevented its surface contacting the medium. The dissolution rates of CUR-HQ, CUR-PB were remarkably enhanced compared to pure curcumin. The CUR-HQ showed more than 83% of curcumin release in pH 6.8 Phosphate buffer and up to 76% release in 0.1 N HCl. whereas CUR-PB shows less release i.e.77% in pH 6.8 and 68% in 0.1 N HCl compared to CUR-HQ.100

CONCLUSION

Though several cocrystallization techniques have been reported in literature, they pose challenges in scale up. In the present investigation, spray drying technique was successfully utilized for the generation of CUR-HQ, CUR- PB. Curcumin co-crystals was prepared with different co-crystal formers to overcome various problems associated with an API. Co-crystals of Curcumin with hydroquinone and p-hydroxy benzoic acid was prepared by using solvent drop grinding method. Co-crystals was confirmed by melting point, ATR-IR, DSC, XRD, NMR. Co-crystals has shown increased solubility. Above study successfully demonstrated the use of cocrystallization an emerging approach for enhancement of physicochemical properties of drug.

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